

30 **A systematic review of the occurrence of Arsenic, Lead, Manganese, and Cadmium in drinking**
31 **water systems in Mexico**
32

33 **Abstract:**

34 Toxic metals (TMs) are contaminants that can cause adverse health outcomes at low levels of
35 chronic exposure. A key exposure route to these contaminants may be through drinking water. Arsenic
36 and Manganese are geogenic contaminants that can also occur from industrial waste. Anthropogenic
37 contamination of drinking water from Cadmium-containing fertilizers and Lead-containing pipes and
38 fittings is of concern. Following PRISMA Guidelines, we conducted a systematic review to understand
39 the distribution of TMs in Mexican drinking water. We searched PubMed, EBSCO Global Health, and
40 Web of Science to identify studies published in English after 1968 that measured any TM in drinking
41 water globally, identifying a set of 20,052 papers for screening, last searched in March 2025. A total of
42 138 papers were included that discuss TMs in Mexican drinking water. We found that 62%, 20%, 14%,
43 and 18% of the reported Mexican drinking water samples exceeded the World Health Organization's
44 Guideline Values for Arsenic, Lead, Manganese, and Cadmium, respectively. Overall, there is sufficient
45 evidence to recommend preventive measures to reduce TM exposures, but there is insufficient data to
46 plan targeted remediation. Our study may act as a map for public health practitioners and researchers to
47 identify understudied regions for further review.

48
49 **Keywords:** Toxic Metals, Drinking Water, Arsenic, Lead, Manganese, Cadmium, Mexico, Latin America

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51 Introduction:

52 Toxic metals (TMs) cause detrimental human health outcomes through acute and chronic
53 exposures. Toxic metals of importance to human health include Arsenic (As), Lead (Pb), Manganese
54 (Mn), and Cadmium (Cd), which have World Health Organization (WHO) Guideline Values (GVs) of 10,
55 10, 80, and 3 μL , respectively (1). While exposures occur through several routes, including the inhalation
56 of air pollution (2–4), soil contamination (5,6), and food intake (7–9), ingestion through drinking water is
57 an important contributor to TM exposure (10–16).

58 Chronic exposure to Arsenic is linked to numerous cancers (17–19) and decreased function across
59 multiple organ systems (20–22). Arsenic is most commonly linked to geogenic contamination of water
60 sources, as seen in South Asia (22), though industrial and agricultural pollution may be important sources
61 of contamination.

62 Lead is a known neurotoxin with no determined safe level of exposure (23) that may cause
63 developmental stunting or learning disabilities in exposed children (24). Lead is also linked to the
64 development of many cancers (25) and health issues related to strokes and heart disease (26). Lead
65 contamination of drinking water has largely been linked to the use of lead-containing materials (27,28).
66 Additional contamination of surface waters by industrial waste (29) and deposition of lead-containing air
67 pollution are recognized (30), and there is some evidence of geogenic lead contamination in select
68 settings.

69 While less recognized as a toxic contaminant, chronic Manganese exposure can lead to
70 neurological damage (31) and is linked to a “Parkinsonian-like syndrome” (32). Manganese commonly
71 contaminates drinking water through geogenic routes (33), but it is also released as an industrial waste
72 byproduct (34).

73 Cadmium is linked to kidney (35), bone (36), and eye damage (37), decreased reproductive
74 output (38,39), and a variety of cancers (40–43). Cadmium is often noted as an anthropogenic
75 contaminant in drinking water, as it is used in fertilizers and other industrial activities (1).

76 Mexico offers an opportunity to study the occurrence and exceedance levels of toxic metals in
77 drinking water. Mexico’s population of 132 million has largely urbanized, with 80% living in urban or
78 peri-urban settings (44). The Joint Monitoring Programme for Water Supply, Sanitation, and Hygiene
79 (JMP) indicates high access to “improved” sources of drinking water, with 100% and 97.47% for urban
80 and rural populations, respectively (45). While piped water shortages have been noted in Mexico City
81 (46), their impact on drinking water quality and the selection of alternate sources is unclear. There is
82 likewise a dependence on bottled water (47), whose quality may not be as strictly regulated. Mexico’s
83 economy has become more reliant on the manufacturing and mining industries (48), which may
84 negatively impact drinking water source quality (49). Prior studies synthesizing evidence from Northern
85 Mexico noted that anthropogenic pollution is a major contributor to arsenic, Lead, and Cadmium
86 occurrences (49). A synthesis of all peer-reviewed drinking water quality data in Mexico, with a focus on
87 exceedances beyond the WHO GVs, may identify critical points for future public health interventions.

88 In this systematic review, we seek to characterize the distribution of toxic metal occurrence,
89 specifically Arsenic, Cadmium, Lead, and Manganese in drinking water and the exceedances of the WHO
90 Guideline values, based on peer-reviewed literature. This differs from previous studies of Mexico in that
91 it focuses specifically on the nationwide distribution of the TMs in drinking water. In contrast, previous
92 analyses either examined a region of Mexico or all water sources without disaggregating known drinking
93 sources, thereby making the analysis less relevant to public health. We use data generated as part of a

94 larger systematic review of toxic metals in drinking water in low- and middle-income countries, in which
 95 we found that papers using data from Mexico accounted for 47% of all relevant peer-reviewed TM
 96 observations in Latin America (50,51). We use this dataset to understand differences in urban and rural
 97 drinking water quality and consumers' exposure to Arsenic, Lead, Manganese, and Cadmium, for which
 98 data were most available and geographically distributed.

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101 **Methods:**

102 *Search Strategy*

103 The evaluation of Lead, Arsenic, Manganese, and Cadmium in Mexico is part of the Fisher et al. 2025
 104 (50,51) systematic review of 14 TMs in LMICs. The overall review strategy and methodology are
 105 registered with Prospero (CRD42024566116). In brief, the study searched PubMed, EBSCO Global
 106 Health, and Web of Science initially in 2019 with a search update on March 17, 2025.

107 The initial search generated 58,576 citations for evaluation. Using the DoCTER machine learning
 108 algorithm (52), a batch of these citations was hand-graded as training data to eliminate irrelevant
 109 publications during the title-and-abstract screening step rapidly. The remaining set of 20,052 publications
 110 was uploaded to Covidence for further evaluation. Studies are included in the overall study if they meet
 111 the criteria described in Table 1: published after 1968 in English, contain primary data representing
 112 measurements of at least one TM of interest, and were collected in an LMIC setting. For this study, only
 113 studies that include data from Mexico are included for further analysis. The summary of the search is
 114 shown in Figure 1 below.

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116 Table 1: Inclusion and exclusion criteria for study selection in a systematic review of toxic metals in
 117 drinking water sources in Mexico, with an emphasis on Arsenic, Cadmium, Lead, and Manganese

Inclusion Criteria	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Based in a low- or middle-income country (LMIC, according to the World Bank's Country and Lending Groups) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Further evaluation of only the Mexico Data 2. Provides a quantitative measure of toxic metals and/or metalloids in a water sample 3. Discusses a toxic metal of interest: Antimony, Arsenic, Cadmium, Chromium, Copper, Iron, Lead, Manganese, Mercury, Nickel, Selenium, Uranium 4. TM appears in a drinking water source (or a source likely to be used for drinking, such as groundwater or fresh surface water) 5. Peer-reviewed publication, article, or book chapter written in English since 1969
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Exclusion Criteria	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Duplicate study 2. Non-English Language 3. The study is not based in LMIC, or the setting cannot be determined 4. Does not provide a quantitative measure of any TM of interest 5. TM is not measured in drinking water sources (or sources likely to be used for drinking, such as groundwater or surface water from a water body documented as being a source of drinking water for human settlements) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Example: only measured in sources, food, or diet b. Only measured in nonportable surface or recreational water source c. Only measured in animals, i.e., animal studies d. Only measured in human blood, bone, or tissue i.e., it is a human health assessment e. Only measured in prepared samples or laboratory solutions to which TMs have been added (e.g., in studies focused on the testing of remediation techniques) 6. The study is a commentary or review that does not present primary data
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119 *Data Extraction*

120 Data were extracted from all elements in the initial study, and the subset of papers focusing on Mexico
121 was selected for further analysis. Initially, a trained data team member extracted relevant data, including
122 the initial study characteristics, drinking water sources, sample collection and preservation, field Quality
123 Assurance and Quality Control (QA/QC), laboratory methods, relevant laboratory QA/QC, identified
124 sources of contamination, and information related to the concentrations of each TM in drinking water.
125 The numerical data extracted from each paper included the arithmetic and geometric means, the median,
126 the minimum, the maximum, and the standard deviation. Any numerical data reported as “non-detect” or
127 an equivalent in the initial paper were treated as one-half the reported limit of detection, either within the
128 initial publication itself or using baseline reported values from manufacturers. In cases where statistical
129 information was missing in the initial paper, values were imputed using the methodology outlined in
130 Hozo et al. (53) and exemplified in the previously published toxic metals systematic review in all LMICs
131 (50,51). If locational information was not provided by the initial author, a relative centroid was calculated
132 and imputed by the initial team member to provide latitude and longitude. All data were then reviewed by
133 a second team member before analysis.

134 *Data Analysis*

135 Summary statistics were calculated for all water quality data to make relevant comparisons, including the
136 expected number of samples exceeding the WHO Guideline. Results are further disaggregated by
137 urban/rural/mixed setting, water source type, and contamination source. We also disaggregated the data
138 by targeted status, indicating that the study was conducted in a known-contaminated setting. We
139 evaluated for reported Antimony, Arsenic, Cadmium, Chromium, Copper, Iron, Mercury, Manganese,
140 Nickel, Lead, Selenium, Tin, Uranium, and Zinc concentrations. However, we only report information on

141 Arsenic, Lead, Manganese, and Cadmium, which had the greatest number of studies and observations of
142 those contaminants with WHO GVs.

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Figure 1 - PRISMA Flowchart of studies included in a systematic review of Toxic Metals in drinking water sources in Mexico

152 Results:

153 We retrieved 134 unique studies evaluating TM concentrations in drinking water in Mexico. A
154 further selection to include only observations of Arsenic, Lead, Manganese, and Cadmium yielded 94
155 unique studies. The frequency of relevant publications increased after 2010, with 2019 and 2023 each
156 having eight published studies. From these relevant studies, we extracted 14,497 observations, which are
157 presented in Figure 2 and Tables 2 and 3 by element and study setting. We have the most data for

158 Arsenic, with 8,943 observations. We had 2,081, 1,976, and 1,497 observations for Lead, Manganese, and
 159 Cadmium, respectively.

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 163 *Figure 2 - Characteristics of included studies. (Left) Cumulative studies published on selected toxic*
 164 *metals in Mexican drinking water over time; (Right) Cumulative observations of Arsenic, Lead,*
 165 *Manganese, and Cadmium in Mexican drinking water over time*

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 167 Overall, 62%, 20%, 14%, and 18% of Arsenic, Lead, Manganese, and Cadmium samples,
 168 respectively, exceeded the WHO GV. There were fewer observations of Arsenic in Urban settings than in
 169 Rural settings. For the other metals, approximately 20% of the data came from Rural settings, in
 170 proportion to the Rural population. A further evaluation of Urban and Rural differences, shown in Table
 171 2, notes a substantial difference between the distributions of each metal’s concentrations. Only Arsenic
 172 had a higher percentage of samples exceeding the WHO GV in Rural settings compared to Urban sources.
 173 The data reveal that a higher percentage of samples from Urban settings exceeded the WHO GV for Lead,
 174 Manganese, and Cadmium compared to Rural settings. However, the data may be skewed due to the low
 175 number of observations in Rural settings. An evaluation of all metals is summarized in Tables S1 and S2.

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178 *Table 2 - Summary of data by Urban versus Rural Classification for Arsenic, Lead, Manganese, and*
 179 *Cadmium in Mexican Drinking Water*

Contaminant	Urban/Rural	Total Observations	% Exceedances
As	Urban	3181	54.39
	Rural	3765	66.96
	Mixed	1997	64.89
Pb	Urban	1585	25.62
	Rural	316	4.43

	Mixed	180	0
Mn	Urban	1577	13.95
	Rural	204	1.47
	Mixed	195	28.72
Cd	Urban	1029	26.34
	Rural	269	0
	Mixed	199	0

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183 There is a more even distribution in the number of samples across improved and unimproved
 184 settings compared to the Urban/Rural divide for Lead, Manganese, and Cadmium, seen in Table 3. We
 185 saw relatively similar percentages of samples exceeding both Arsenic and Cadmium in JMP-Improved
 186 and JMP-Unimproved settings. There were higher percentages of samples exceeding both Lead and
 187 Manganese in JMP-Unimproved settings.

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189 *Table 3 - Summary of data by JMP Improved versus Unimproved Classification for Arsenic, Lead,*
 190 *Manganese, and Cadmium in Mexican Drinking Water*

Contaminant	Improved/Unimproved	Total Observations	% Exceedances
As	Improved	5295	61.25
	Unimproved	3648	63.16
Pb	Improved	1004	13.35
	Unimproved	1077	26.56
Mn	Improved	1009	9.42
	Unimproved	967	19.03
Cd	Improved	605	19.83

	Unimproved	892	16.93
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The spatial distributions of exceedance percentages for Arsenic, Lead, Manganese, and Cadmium are shown in Figures 3, 4, 5, and 6, respectively. Arsenic has the widest coverage of sampling sites, though there are none in the Baja Peninsula and only 3 studies in the Southeast and Yucatan regions. Studies report exceedances of Arsenic in more than 40% of samples in almost every region studied. Lead and Manganese are sparsely represented, with a concentration of studies around Mexico City. Manganese, especially, seems to have higher exceedance rates in the area around the Valley of Mexico. Cadmium has the fewest studies and the sparsest coverage, with no discernible geographic trend.

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Figure 3 - Distribution of the percentages of Arsenic exceeding the WHO Guideline Value of 10 µg/L in Mexican Drinking Water. The size of circles corresponds to the number of observations.

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Figure 4 - Distribution of the percentages of Lead exceeding the WHO Guideline Value of 10 µg/L in Mexican Drinking Water. The size of circles corresponds to the number of observations.

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Figure 5 - Distribution of the percentages of Manganese exceeding the provisional WHO Guideline Value of 80 µg/L in Mexican Drinking Water. The size of circles corresponds to the number of observations.

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 216 *Figure 6 - Distribution of the percentages of Cadmium exceeding the WHO Guideline Value of 3 µg/L in*
 217 *Mexican Drinking Water. The size of circles corresponds to the number of observations.*
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220 **Discussion:**

221 Toxic metals exceed WHO guideline values across Mexico, with substantial public health
 222 consequences. Of notable concern is Arsenic, which had high exceedances in all evaluated setting types:
 223 urban and rural, improved and unimproved. While 62% of all Arsenic samples exceeded the WHO GV, a
 224 further disaggregation of the 1655 Arsenic samples from piped water sources with available data showed
 225 that 59% exceeded the GV, indicating that this source is not exempt from contamination. The distribution
 226 of Arsenic exceedances does not appear to show a specific geographic pattern, suggesting that
 227 contamination may be widespread. The high level of Arsenic exceedances in improved sources may
 228 indicate geogenic contamination of groundwater sources. However, the original studies indicated that
 229 both anthropogenic and geogenic sources contributed to contamination at similar rates, including in
 230 targeted and non-targeted studies.

231 The percentage of exceedances in Lead, Manganese, and Cadmium is also at levels of public
 232 health concern, with more than 10% of samples exceeding the relevant WHO Guideline Values for
 233 drinking water concentrations. Almost all studies that specified a source of Lead reported anthropogenic
 234 contamination, whereas studies that specified a source for Manganese and Cadmium reported both
 235 anthropogenic and geogenic contamination at similar rates. Considering the JMP data, which indicates
 236 that over 95% of Mexico depends on improved sources, it is unclear what this exposure from unimproved
 237 sources means for public health. The higher level of Lead exceedances in unimproved sources, at double
 238 the frequency observed in improved systems, suggests industrial contamination of less-protected sources,
 239 such as surface water and springs, beyond baseline contamination from infrastructure components, though
 240 this needs further review.

241 While there may be enough evidence to advocate for national action on Lead, Manganese, and
242 Cadmium contamination, occurrence data are scarce in many regions. Systematic sampling may be
243 necessary to identify hotspots of contamination where remediation should take place for each metal. For
244 Arsenic and Manganese, which are often noted as geogenic contaminants in the literature (33), selective
245 sampling where there is a spatial gap in groundwater quality data may enable kriging or an equivalent
246 geospatial analysis to characterize a wider range of communities. Likewise, some geogenic sources of
247 Cadmium could be better mapped by collecting additional groundwater quality data in areas where
248 evidence is currently lacking. As Cadmium is linked to fertilizers and industrial contamination, mapping
249 of intensive agriculture and industrial sites could identify points for preventative action (9,40,41). Lead
250 contamination, which is often from lead-containing drinking infrastructure, may require a deeper
251 evaluation of the actual building materials to develop interventions (14). Therefore, the next step after
252 systematic groundwater quality sampling in understudied locations may involve the mapping of
253 industrial, mining, and agricultural sites through citizen science or outright policy, building on the
254 evidence noted elsewhere (48,49). More data is needed to conduct targeted interventions and remediate
255 toxic metals in drinking water in Mexico. Many urban and rural areas of Mexico have not been
256 characterized in the peer-reviewed literature; therefore, an intentional intervention in these areas may be
257 poorly informed. Instead, this review of Mexican data should act as a map for researchers to evaluate
258 understudied settings.

259 Some efforts are already underway to map and identify potential sources of anthropogenic
260 contamination in Mexico. Anthropogenic activity is characterized by industries including manufacturing
261 and mining, agriculture and fertilizer use, fuel combustion, smelting, and urban wastewater discharge
262 (54). Rapid industrialization, urbanization, and population growth have led to increased wastewater
263 discharge in Mexico (55). Literature suggests that these activities could be sources of Arsenic, Lead,
264 Manganese, and Cadmium contamination in drinking water (54). Groundwater overexploitation is an
265 anthropogenic activity of note for arsenic because it significantly increases contamination by favoring the
266 release of arsenic from geogenic sources, through pressure on minerals like sulfides and oxyhydroxides
267 surrounding the water flow (56). Over-pumping groundwater sources is meant to address growing
268 demand for drinking water as Mexico faces aquifer depletion, drought, and population growth, but
269 increased access does not guarantee increased safe access (56,57). Mining is also highly associated with
270 arsenic contamination in drinking water across the country (56). Industrial and agricultural waste in
271 Mexico is regulated by the Ministry of Environment, Natural Resources and Fishing (SEMARNAT),
272 the General Law on Appropriate and Sustainable Food, and the General Law for the Prevention and
273 Integral Management of Wastes (58–60). Waste and wastewater permissible limits are regulated by
274 Mexican Official Environmental Standards (NOMs) and the National Water Commission (CONAGUA)
275 (58). A review of sources from these federal agencies may yield crucial information for public health
276 surveillance planning.

277 Though we note the gaps in the geographic distribution of data, this is not unique to Mexico. The
278 global systematic review from which we selected this subset of data notes that Mexico has the most
279 studies published evaluating Toxic Metals across Latin America. The need for additional water quality
280 data on toxic metals is global to identify and prevent exposures at public health concern levels.
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282 Limitations

283 While this review was extensive, it has not exhausted all potential datasets. The study, by design,
284 did not include grey literature, which may provide further context on understudied locations, though the
285 methodologies from this literature set must be verified as capable of producing reliable water-quality data.
286 There are likely datasets that were not included due to the restriction to English-language studies. To
287 avoid the upward bias in observed concentrations, we excluded papers that lacked adequate
288 instrumentation for measuring the specified toxic metals. Additionally, we did not have the raw data to
289 evaluate each sample individually, so we relied on imputation to fill gaps in exceedance data using the
290 Hozo et al. methodology and modeling (53). Raw datasets of each study would enable an exact
291 calculation of the proportion of exceedances rather than an estimate. Similarly, we relied on the centroid
292 of each study's sample location to represent it graphically, which could be improved with raw datasets to
293 map each point of coverage.

296 Conclusion:

297 In this study, we evaluated the occurrence and distribution of TMs in drinking water in Mexico
298 through a systematic review. From our 94-identified studies, we have found sufficient evidence to
299 advocate for efforts to prevent the contamination of drinking water by Arsenic, Lead, Manganese, and
300 Cadmium. This may require strengthening policies and regulations to protect existing drinking water
301 sources or identifying potential routes of contamination. We also identified the potential challenges in
302 addressing existing contamination due to a lack of data in many parts of the country. While there are
303 many geographic regions without accessible peer-reviewed TM data, Mexico has a foundation with its
304 existing evidence to continue its progress in limiting and eliminating exposures through drinking water.

307 Statements and Declarations

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329 **References:**

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